

Potentiometric Studies on Quaternary Complexes of Dioxouranium(VI)

VINOD KUMARI and G. K. CHATURVEDI

Chemical Laboratories, Agra College, Agra. (India)

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The formation of quaternary complexes of dioxouranium(VI) with three different organic acids (OX, MALN and SA, SSA, TAR or TMA) has been inferred from the potentiometric studies. The formation constants for the resulting triligand complexes have been evaluated.

THE binary systems of dioxouranium(VI) with carboxylic or hydroxy acids have been extensively studied by several workers¹⁻¹⁰. Although dioxouranium ion tends to form ternary^{11,12} and quaternary¹³ complexes in preference to 1:2 or 1:3 binary species due to delayed hydrolysis and polymerisation, insignificant amount of work has been carried out on these systems. It was, therefore, considered of great interest to study some of the ternary and quaternary systems such as UO₂(II)-OX-MALN-SA/SSA/TAR/TMA (where OX=oxalic, MALN=malonic, SA=salicylic, SSA=5-sulfosalicylic, TAR=tartaric and TMA=thiomalic acid), potentiometrically with a view of characterizing and evaluating the formation constants of the resulting mixed ligand species.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of BDH Analar grade. The stock solution of UO₂(NO₃)₂ was prepared and the metal estimated gravimetrically as U₃O₈. The ligand solutions were prepared by direct weighing and the concentrations of the solutions were checked by potentiometric titrations against 0.1 M KOH. The concentrations of the solutions (5 × 10⁻³ M in metal or ligand), total volume (50 ml) and ionic strength (μ = 0.1 M KNO₃) were always kept constant at the beginning of the titration.

pH measurements were made with Philips precision pH meter (PR 9405 M) using standard glass (PV 9011) and calomel (PV 9021) electrodes. The instrument was standardized against 0.05 M potassium hydrogen phthalate for pH-4 at temperature 25 ± 1° before use.

Calculations :

The dissociation constants (table 1) were calculated by the method of Chaberek and Martell¹⁴ or Noyes¹⁵ and the formation constants by the method of Ramamoorthy and Santappa according to which in the

TABLE-1

Ligand	pK ₁	pK ₂
Oxalic acid	1.66	3.90
Malonic acid	2.75	5.36
Salicylic acid	2.99	13.60
Sulfosalicylic acid ^d	2.68	11.42
Tartaric acid	2.52	4.16
Thiomalic acid	3.01	4.51

TABLE-2

System	log K _{MLL'L''3}
UO ₂ -OX-MALN-SA	16.00 ± 0.14
UO ₂ -OX-MALN-SSA	11.13 ± 0.19
UO ₂ -OX-MALN-TAR	13.50 ± 0.15
UO ₂ -OX-MALN-TMA	12.09 ± 0.18

case of M(II)-dibasic-dibasic-monobasic acid system¹⁶

$$K_{MLL'L''} = \frac{T_M - 3[A]X}{\left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^4 [A]^4 X}$$

$$\text{where } [A] = \frac{5T_M - T_{OH} - [H^+]}{\frac{3[H^+]}{k_2 + k_2' + k_1'} + \frac{4[H^+]^2}{k_1 k_2 + k_1' k_2'}}$$

$$X = 1 + \frac{3[H^+]}{k_2 + k_2' + k_1'} + \frac{2[H^+]^2}{k_1 k_2 + k_1' k_2'}$$

where T_{OH} = [KOH], T_M = [Metal]total, k₁' = dissociation constant of monobasic acid and k₁, k₂ and k₁' and k₂' are the first and second dissociation constants of dibasic acids.

and in the case of M(II)-dibasic-dibasic-dibasic acid system^{1,3}

$$K_{MLL'L''} = \frac{T_M - \frac{1}{3}[A]X}{\left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^4 [A]^4 X}$$

$$[A] = \frac{6T_M - T_{OH} - [H^+]}{6[H^+]^2} \cdot \frac{1}{k_1 k_2 + k_1' k_2' + k_1'' k_2''} + \frac{3[H^+]}{k_2 + k_2' + k_2''}$$

$$X = 1 + \frac{3[H^+]^2}{k_1 k_2 + k_1' k_2' + k_1'' k_2''} + \frac{3[H^+]}{k_2 + k_2' + k_2''}$$

$k_1 k_2$, $k_1' k_2'$ and k_1'' and k_2'' being the first and second dissociation constants of the three dibasic acids respectively.

Hydrolysis and polymerisation of the complexes was supposed to be negligible in the pH range in which calculations were made (pH 2-3).

Results and Discussion

The curve representing the pH metric titration of $UO_2(NO_3)_2$ with KOH is similar to that obtained by Feldman *et al.*¹⁷, a sharp inflection observed at $m \sim 2.3$ (m =moles of alkali added per mole of metal or ligand) being attributed to the species such as $U_2O_8^{2+}$, $U_3O_8^{3+}$, $U_3O_8(OH)^+$, $U_3O_8(OH)_2$ etc.

Fig. 1. UO_2 - OX - MALN - SA system
 Curve a = 1:1 UO_2 - SA, a' = 1:1 UO_2 - OX,
 a'' = 1:1 UO_2 - MALN,
 b = 1:1:1 UO_2 - OX - SA, b' = 1:1:1 UO_2 - OX
 - MALN,
 c = 1:1:1:1 UO_2 - OX - MALN - SA

Fig. 2. $UO_2(II)$ - OX - MALN - SSA system
 Curve a = 1:1 UO_2 - SSA, b = 1:1:1 UO_2 - OX - SSA,
 c = 1:1:1:1 UO_2 - OX - MALN - SSA

Fig. 3. $UO_2(II)$ - OX - MALN - TAR system
 Curve a = 1:1 UO_2 - TAR, b = 1:1:1 UO_2 - OX - TAR,
 c = 1:1:1:1 UO_2 - OX - MALN - TAR

Fig. 4. $UO_2(II)$ -OX-MALN-TMA system
 Curve a=1:1 UO_2 -TMA, b=1:1:1 UO_2 -OX-TMA,
 c=1:1:1:1 UO_2 -OX-MALN-TMA

Curves a', a" (fig. 1) and a (figs. 1-4) represent the titration of 1 : 1 UO_2 -OX/MALN and UO_2 -SA/SSA/TAR/TMA systems respectively. The lowering in pH in comparison to free ligands, colour changes and inflection at $m \sim 2$ in the case of UO_2 -OX/MALN/SA/SSA may be attributed to the formation of 1 : 1 complexes which, however, undergo hydrolysis and polymerisation^{17,18} at higher pH forming species having U-O-U

case of UO_2 -OX/MALN) and at $m \sim 3.5$ (in case of UO_2 -SA/SSA) may be ascribed to such changes. In the case of UO_2 -TAR/TMA, the first inflection at $m \sim 3$ may probably indicate the formation of binary species by the deprotonation of two carboxy and one hydroxy or mercapto group of acids.

Curve b' (fig. 1) and b (figs. 1-4) represent the titration of 1 : 1 : 1 UO_2 -OX-MALN and UO_2 -OX-SA/SSA/TAR/TMA systems respectively (curves representing similar ternary systems such as UO_2 -MALN-SA/SSA/TAR/TMA have been omitted in the figs. for the sake of brevity) and curve c (figs. 1-4) represent 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 UO_2 -OX-MALN-SA/SSA/TAR/TMA systems. The lowering in pH, difference in precipitation pH's, significant colour changes probably indicate the formation of ternary and quaternary species. The composition of the ternary and quaternary complexes were assumed to be 1 : 1 : 1 and 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 respectively since neither of the acids on being titrated separately in the

presence of equimolar amount of UO_2^{2+} appeared to exhibit the tendency of forming binary complexes other than 1 : 1.

The single inflection and gradual deepening of the colour support the simultaneous addition of the three ligands to the metal ion resulting in the equilibrium $M + L + L' + L'' \rightleftharpoons MLL'L''$. Calculations have been made assuming that oxalic, malonic, thiomalic and tartaric acid act as dibasic acids and salicylic and sulfosalicylic as monobasic acids in the case of quaternary systems.

A comparison of stability constants indicate that quaternary complexes containing SA and TAR are more stable than complexes consisting of SSA and TMA respectively.

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